
EUROSCITIZEN COST ACTION - VIRTUAL NETWORKING SUPPORT GRANT 2021

Guidelines for **Grant Holder (GH) Managers** of **Virtual COST Meetings**

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Authors:

Joelyn de Lima, Lilian Smith

Please note – meetings and the budget for the moderation support (Local Organiser Support) need to be approved by the MC and COST before being planned

Zoom Account Login Details	1
Potential moderators	1
At least 15 days before the event	1
At least 14 days before the event	1
Within 10 day of the event	2

Zoom Account Login Details

Will be provided by the respective WG leader as and when needed

Potential moderators

A list of potential moderators is being assembled. However, please feel free to engage any moderator you prefer. Please make sure to contact them well in advance. It is your responsibility to enroll a moderator that suits your needs (language/availability/costs).

At least 15 days before the event

- Information received from the Meeting Organiser about the following details:
 - Meeting title
 - Date(s) and Time(s)
 - List of participants to be invited through eCOST
 - Estimated moderation costs
- Information received from the Moderator about the following details:
 - Zoom link

At least 14 days before the event

- Send out the event invitations through eCOST
- Encode GH institution as Local Organiser and set the Local Organiser Support (LOS) budget to the estimated moderation costs
- Send LOS for approval by MC-Chair (or MC Vice-Chair)

Within 10 day of the event

- Make sure to have received the invoice and list of attendees from the Moderator
- Confirm meeting participants in eCOST
- Upload attendance list in eCOST
- Encode LOS in eCOST according to Vademecum, section 7.1.5 and section 7.2
- Pay moderators invoice through normal channels of GH institution
- Reimburse GH institution through COST funds